

**ACTIVITIES OF WORKING WITH WOMEN'S IN INTERNAL
AFFAIRS BODIES OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: The article examines the first Uzbek woman police officer and her service activities. Also, the number of women working in the systems of internal affairs bodies in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the work being carried out on the prevention of possible crimes and violations have been analyzed.

Key words: Roziya Otajonova, internal affairs body, reform, decision, Ministry of Internal Affairs, inspector, rehabilitation, protection order, penal institutions, administrative responsibility.

In the history of Uzbek statehood, the active role of prominent women in social and political relations is clearly visible. Tomir Khotun, Kabaj Khotun, Saraymulkhanim, Gavharshadbegim and many other historical figure have a special role in the past of our country and of our people, but there is one factor that unites them all. In any case, they devoted their life to serving our country and nation.

Today, in our country, all important regulations regarding the glorification of women, their economic, social and political activity, and increasing their influence in the society, are being introduced to enable women to acquire knowledge, to show their talents and abilities.

Large- scale reforms in terms of training and employment of women, involving women in bussiness, increasing their role in this field, social support, protection of women in need, and ensuring gender equality are being implemented [2].

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, during his speech at the event which was held for the International Women's Day on March 8, said that 45% of the employees in various

fields and networks in our country are women, and there are about 1,400 leadership positions in the system of state and public organizations, 17 of them Senator, 16 of them are deputies of the Legislative Chamber of Oliy Majlis, 1 thousand 75 people's deputies are active in local councils [3].

The women of our country have shown that they are capable of taking part in the development of the state, contributing to the development of entrepreneurship and economic sphere, and showing their talent in the development of science, along with bringing up their children. For instance, there are many women working in internal affairs bodies as well as in all areas of society .

Roziya Otajonova is considered to be the first Uzbek policewoman who served in the internal affairs system for the peace of the country. She was born in 1904 in the village of Gozovot, Koshkopir district, Khorezm region, in the family of Otajon, who was a peasant. He had 3 children.

In 1924, peasant police departments were established to maintain public safety and protect the population from internal and external enemies.

In 1925, Roziya Otajonova was accepted to the police because she was a beautiful, tall, strong, brave, determined woman.

During her 21 years of work in the police system, Roziya Otajonova joined the volunteer police squad, seriously approached her duties, and bravely fought with criminal gangs to maintain public order. She alone tracked down a notorious criminal who was a big spy in the Ghazovot region, and caught him with physical evidence. She worked in Gozovot, Khiva and Pitnak departments of the police.

Later, she and her family settled in “Pakhtakor” neighborhood, Gozovot village, Koshkopir district, Khorezm region. Roziya Otajonova died on January 21, 1979. She was buried in the “Bakirjon Bobo” cemetery in the village [4].

The female employees of the internal affairs bodies honor the name of Roziya Otajonova and acknowledge her courage and bravery during her service. Currently, female employees like Roziya Otajonova, who serve in the system, make up 10.2 percent of the personnel.

This figure is 10% in the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpagistan, 10% in the Departments of Internal Affairs of Bukhara and Jizzakh regions, 7% in the Departments of Internal Affairs of Andijan, Navoi and Khorezm regions, 7.4% in the Department of Internal Affairs of Kashkadarya Region, 6% in the Department of Internal Affairs of Namangan Region, Samarkand Region 5.3 percent in the Department of Internal Affairs, 5.1 percent in the Department of Internal Affairs of Surkhandarya region, 8 percent in the Department of Internal Affairs of Syrdarya region, in Tashkent It is 6.2 percent in the Head office of Internal Affairs of the region, 4.8 percent in Internal Affairs of Fargona region and 7.5 percent in the Head office of Internal Affairs of Tashkent city [5].

In recent years, women have been recognized as equal representatives in all spheres of life and activity of our society, and a unique system of working with women has been established. Reforms in this regard are systematically carried out and put into practice in internal affairs bodies as well as in all spheres of society.

In particular, the position of inspector on issues of working with women was introduced in the systems of the Ministry of Internal Affairs [6], and the task of organizing activities aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms and legal interests of women has been assigned as the responsibility of the inspector. As a result, this enabled to solve women's socio- economic problems, that is, during the past 2022, on the initiative of the internal affairs bodies, 6 849 (429 of whom were previously convicted) women were employed and 6 315 women (406 of whom were previously convicted) received financial and social help. 1 504 women (96 of them with previous convictions) received medical assistance, 1 767 women (105 of them with previous convictions) had their identity documents restored, 2 136 women (72 of them were reprimanded) were given opportunities to engage in business activities, and 402 women were sent to “The center of women’s rehabilitation and adaption”.

The problems of 30 356 families with conflicts were settled by responsible people in their neighbourhood itself, the problems of 21 798 families were resolved, and 8 658 divorces were avoided.

30 720 women, including 827 minors and 5,716 young girls (18-30), were transferred to a healthy lifestyle as a result of joint preventive measures and were removed from the preventive account of the internal affairs bodies

In turn, one of the important issues is that today women are faced with oppression or violence, and this expression was not used before, and as a result, some women did not know who to turn to for this issue.

Starting from 2020, the practice of giving protection warrants to women who suffered from oppression and violence was established, and the victims were taken into state custody. As a result, during the year 2022, 49 774 women who were subjected to violence were identified, and all of them were given "protection warrants" and consequently 25 239 family problems were solved, 20887 real causes of problematic situations were settled down.

In turn, 2 813 people who did not follow the established restrictions, were not affected by the preventive measures and did not draw the correct conclusions for themselves, 206 m) are subject to administrative liability.

15 women who have been served prison terms will be employed for the purpose of providing employment for women who have served their sentences. 60 hours of training on business skills has been provided to 116 women, and it is planned to train 100 students per month in these training courses.

Also, a joint project "Detained in Penitentiary Institutions, Probation, and Sentenced Women", which provides for the provision of employment by teaching competitive professions in the labor market to the women, who have been sentenced and served their prison terms, as well as solves the problems which they are facing was established.

In addition, in cooperation with official ministries, a social- psychological support plan for the years 2022-2023 was developed for the families of women who left their place of residence for a period of time.

Also, in order to quickly provide necessary assistance to women who have fallen into a difficult situation, a small "Trust Center" numbered "1259" has been established

in the system (as part of the Crime Prevention Service, from January 10 2022, and more than 12 thousand (12 767) citizens who applied to this center in the past period were given legal advice and 11 656 women were provided with psychological and legal assistance.

A total of 18 794 events were held in neighborhoods and organizations on the topic of ending violence against women, 2 370 of which were sports events, 5 124 were cultural events, and 11300 were educational events. 7 326 of them were held in enterprises and organizations, 27 426 of them were in neighbourhoods and 15 772 of them were held in educational institutions [9].

In general, It is of high importance to raise brave and courageous boys who are loyal to the Motherland, girls with high spirituality, to have reliable security the country, the women of the country should be vigilant and so should neighbourhood and community. Only then will it be easier for us to achieve the goals and tasks set in the development strategy for the further development of Uzbekistan, which is being implemented today.

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